

Dimension

Level

Leadership and Governance

Basic

B

Entrepreneurship as Part of HEI Strategy

Actions & Formats	Timespan
Create a concrete action plan that includes your commitments and encourages you to continuously include entrepreneurship in your HEI strategy discussions.	Medium-term
Setting up an internal entrepreneurship platform facilitates collaboration and elaboration of your entrepreneurship strategy.	Medium-term

1

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Leadership and Governance

Basic

B

Entrepreneurship as Part of HEI Strategy

For entrepreneurship to thrive within your HEI, you should consider making it part of your institution's overall strategic plan. In this way, you legitimize entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial behaviour within your HEI. This will make it easier to disseminate entrepreneurship across existing divides, schools, departments, and also to ingrain entrepreneurship across curricula and subject groups.

Formalising this process by defining a concrete action plan that involves entrepreneurship in your future strategy will make these developments transparent to internal stakeholders and interest groups.

An additional internal, interdisciplinary entrepreneurship platform should be used to invite participation from all disciplines as well as external stakeholders. This platform may be used to elaborate on action plans, invite interested groups to participate in the strategy process, and establish a community of entrepreneurship practice and research within your HEI.

Related Cards

Entrepreneurship as the Core of HEI Strategy 4

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2 Builder, 3 Educator

1

XVI

Number ↑

Entrepreneurship as Part of HEI Strategy

Actions & Formats

Create a concrete action plan that includes your commitments and encourages you to continuously include entrepreneurship in your HEI strategy discussions.

Setting up an internal entrepreneurship platform facilitates collaboration and elaboration of your entrepreneurship strategy.

Timespan

Medium-term

Medium-term

Entrepreneurship as Part of HEI Strategy

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Related Cards

Entrepreneurship as the Core of HEI Strategy **4**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2 Builder, **3** Educator

Regular Reflection

Actions & Formats

Use the HEInnovate framework and self-assessment tool to continuously identify and prioritise next steps and overall strategy.

Survey experts from within your organisation to keep up to date with current developments.

Lead open discussion with internal and external stakeholders to co-create your HEI strategy.

Timespan

Short-term

Short-term

Short-term

Regular Reflection

Developing and implementing an entrepreneurial agenda requires regular reflection and collective introspection.

The HEInnovate framework and self-assessment tool can help guide you through a process of identifying and prioritising your HEI's innovative potential, as well as planning improvement actions.

In addition to the structured HEInnovate self-assessment tool, you might also employ other ways of surveying the opinions and progress of your internal entrepreneurship experts and stakeholders. To acknowledge different perspectives, ensure you include a diverse selection of individuals from various sectors and functions of your organisation to highlight discrepancies in opinion and level of development.

Any findings or insights should be relayed to your HEI's internal entrepreneurship community as a catalyst for open discussion about your HEI's entrepreneurship mindset and practices.

Related Cards

Entrepreneurship as Part of the HEI strategy **1**

Entrepreneurship as the Core of the HEI Strategy **4**

Applicable Profiles

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

1 Entrepreneurial Aspirant

Encourage Entrepreneurship

Actions & Formats

Foster top-down/senior management encouragement for entrepreneurship activities.

Create dedicated outlets, such as blogs and websites, to encourage updates about entrepreneurship activities at your HEI.

Timespan

Short-term

Medium-term

Encourage Entrepreneurship

Being entrepreneurial is not easy. It is hard work and requires prolonged dedication and effort. It also requires proper support. Positive reassurance from peers and superiors can have a significant positive impact. Entrepreneurship at HEIs, therefore, is enacted through supportive leadership and continuous encouragement.

Encouragement can also be provided by highlighting previous success stories. Dedicated websites as well as internal and external blogs provide an interactive and engaging medium to showcase entrepreneurial achievements at your HEI.

Related Cards

Teaching Assessments **8**

Extracurricular Teaching Formats **13**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

1 Entrepreneurial Aspirant

Entrepreneurship as the Core of HEI Strategy

Actions & Formats

Focus your future HEI development on entrepreneurship and make it a primary mission/strategic goal.

Timespan

Medium-term

Feature entrepreneurship as one of the main themes in internal and external communication channels.

Medium-term

Entrepreneurship as the Core of HEI Strategy

Entrepreneurship bridges disciplinary divides in HEIs and brings together internal and external interest groups. Entrepreneurship is also inherently forward-looking and is concerned with creating a desirable future for everyone.

Given these fundamental traits and benefits, several HEIs have incorporated entrepreneurship across all areas of their strategy, and as an important part of their future strategy development.

Putting entrepreneurship at the core of your HEI strategy requires an honest assessment of your current capabilities and existing regional entrepreneurial ecosystem. Your primary mission should reflect how you intend to incorporate entrepreneurship: as a research discipline, as an economic growth mechanism, or as a motivation tool for your students.

Your strategic focus on entrepreneurship should also guide your communication plan and, therefore, be one of the main themes featured throughout all communication channels.

To help overcome internal barriers, the HEI may consider including additional support activities to showcase and encourage entrepreneurship.

Related Cards

Entrepreneurship as Part of HEI Strategy **1**
Centres for Entrepreneurship **6**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2 Builder, **3** Educator

Entrepreneurship Board or Council

Actions & Formats

Form an entrepreneurship council that brings together local key stakeholders.

Create an entrepreneurship board to challenge and mentor your organisation. Include internal decision-makers and external stakeholders on the board.

Set up a scientific council of advisors to advance your entrepreneurship research agenda.

Timespan

Medium-term

Medium-term

Long-term

Entrepreneurship Board or Council

Regular checks by external stakeholders and experts can provide necessary feedback to craft a realistic yet ambitious entrepreneurship strategy for your HEI. An entrepreneurship board or council can provide non-binding strategic advice to your HEI, interest group or department.

An internal entrepreneurship board could comprise relevant stakeholders, such as vice-presidents, rectors and deans who provide context-specific counsel and help with supporting new initiatives. An external board may consist of national and international entrepreneurship experts who can provide strategic insights into current developments within the field.

A regional entrepreneurship council made up of local industry representatives, politicians and other relevant stakeholders can help connect your activities to the existing local entrepreneurial ecosystem.

If you are part of a research-driven HEI, setting up a scientific council may provide valuable guidance on strengthening your international research profile.

Related Cards

Entrepreneurship as the Core of HEI Strategy **4**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 **4** 5 6 7

4 Internal Performer, **5** Regional Performer,
6 International Performer, **7** Guru

Centres for Entrepreneurship

Actions & Formats

Create an informal hub or a more formal group or department for entrepreneurship.

Establish an entrepreneurship centre as a central place for your entrepreneurship activities.

Merge entrepreneurship activities and create synergies between different initiatives at your HEI.

Timespan

Medium-term

Long-term

Long-term

Centres for Entrepreneurship

In large organisations, it is important to balance centralised coordination with decentralised grassroots initiatives. Creating dedicated spaces for entrepreneurship within a HEI provides a “home” for entrepreneurial activities that pursue a long-term strategy. It can also nurture and facilitate smaller and ad-hoc entrepreneurship endeavours across the HEI.

Such dedicated spaces for entrepreneurship could take the form of informal and decentralised entrepreneurship hubs or a dedicated entrepreneurship department. Higher education institutions with pronounced entrepreneurship ambitions may also decide to set-up a dedicated centralised entrepreneurship centre which merges and aligns the HEI’s activities.

With a dedicated home for entrepreneurship in place, it becomes easier to coordinate large-scale collaborations with industry partners and other HEIs to spread the impact beyond your own organisation.

Related Cards

Entrepreneurship as the Core of HEI Strategy **4**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 **4** 5 6 7

4 Internal Performer, **5** Regional Performer,
6 International Performer, **7** Guru

Support for Entrepreneurship Initiatives

Actions & Formats

Timespan

Be supportive towards new entrepreneurship projects and initiatives.

Short-term

Identify collaborators to experiment with and launch new entrepreneurship initiatives.

Short-term

Enable entrepreneurship educators and coaches to provide peer support and collaboration to improve your programmes and service offerings.

Medium-term

Support for Entrepreneurship Initiatives

A supportive environment is beneficial to help entrepreneurship initiatives thrive in HEIs. Having a dedicated group of people as a source of motivation and intellectual inspiration helps the HEI follow-through on its entrepreneurial vision.

Such groups can provide support for new entrepreneurship projects such as launching new start-up support offerings, entrepreneurship events, student clubs or new partnerships with industry and established start-ups.

A support group of educators can provide peer-support relating to each other's teaching styles and pedagogical approach. Such a group may decide to collaborate on creating and offering joint entrepreneurship modules and courses to increase the consistency of entrepreneurship education across departments and faculties. Encouraging links between other faculties can help embed entrepreneurship across all disciplines and encourage the development of an entrepreneurial mindset.

Related Cards

Entrepreneurship as Part of HEI Strategy **1**
Entrepreneurship as the Core of HEI Strategy **4**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2 Builder

Teaching Assessments

Actions & Formats

Regularly assess the quality and impact of your entrepreneurship education offerings.

Incorporate peer-feedback from other experienced colleagues into teaching assessments.

Develop a tool or mechanism that educators can use to keep track of their personal objectives and impact.

Timespan

Short-term

Short-term

Medium-term

Teaching Assessments

Assessing the quality and impact of entrepreneurship education is a useful mechanism to improve educational interventions.

A HEI can evaluate students' experiences and development by administering a basic survey at the end of the entrepreneurship programme. There are several validated frameworks available to help with this (see related card).

Educators can also establish the specific objective they want to achieve. This can be an informal process or conducted via a formalised digital goal-setting and evaluation tool. With regard to the latter, it is possible to tie these personal goals to a personalised staff development plan. Educators may augment this by incorporating peer-feedback from other experienced colleagues.

It is also advised to incorporate industry representatives, where possible, for assessments. Additionally, the HEI may identify a format for evaluation that is internationally recognised.

Related Cards

Student Experience Evaluation **37**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2 Builder, **3** Educator

Establish Entrepreneurial Roles

Actions & Formats

Introduce dedicated leadership roles for entrepreneurship at your HEI.

Create academic and leadership split positions where a person divides their time between both.

Adjust the career paths in your HEI to include development options for entrepreneurial roles.

Timespan

Medium-term

Medium-term

Long-term

Establish Entrepreneurial Roles

Becoming a more entrepreneurial HEI is not a simple task. Systemic complexities, existing boundaries between faculties and departments, and restrictive guidelines for staff can hold back a HEI's overall entrepreneurial development.

A feasible way of cutting through these challenges is to establish dedicated leadership roles. These roles should be clearly defined, evaluated in terms of impact, have serious input into higher level decision making and be sustainable.

The roles should be filled with entrepreneurial individuals who are provided with the means and authority to lead the implementation of entrepreneurial activities throughout the HEI. This requires modifying possible career paths for entrepreneurial leaders and the creation of transparent criteria for this new staff profile.

One possible way to establish more entrepreneurial roles within your HEI is to create split roles. For example, a qualified person could split their time between a part-time professorship role and a part-time leadership role at your HEI's entrepreneurship centre to bridge potential disconnected positions.

Related Cards

Entrepreneurship as the Core of HEI Strategy **4**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 **4** 5 6 7

4 Internal Performer, **5** Regional Performer,
6 International Performer

Entrepreneurship Funding

Actions & Formats

Participate in relevant projects via national or international public tenders.

Actively research new sources of funding for entrepreneurship initiatives.

Cooperate with established companies and raise funds through industry collaboration.

Build up an endowment through private or industry donations or individual patrons.

Timespan

Medium-term

Medium-term

Medium-term

Long-term

Entrepreneurship Funding

Expanding entrepreneurship activities within a HEI generally requires developing a steady stream of funding.

This may initially require active research to identify creative new ways of developing funding streams through less formal mediums (for example, via student projects or collaboration with industry).

Additional funds could be secured by submitting proposals for national or international public tenders. In many cases, this requires you to work with other HEIs as part of a consortium. Make sure that your proposal is in-line with your overall entrepreneurship strategy.

Offering services directly to industry may be another source of funding. Several HEIs offer training, consulting or contract research services directly to industry partners. Services could also include paid student projects or matching companies with relevant start-ups in their field.

In the long-term, building up an endowment specifically for entrepreneurship activities at your HEI can create a steady income stream in addition to existing funding sources.

Related Cards

Support for Entrepreneurship Initiatives **7**

Start-up Funding **20**

Industry Collaboration **28**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 **4** 5 6 7

4 Internal Performer, **5** Regional Performer,

6 International Performer, **7** Guru

Teach the Teacher

Actions & Formats

Participate in peer-mentoring with other educators to provide mutual support and guidance.

Organise “Train the Trainer” programmes/ workshops to exchange learning and experiences with other educators.

Join one of the existing entrepreneurship education networks to engage with the wider community.

Timespan

Short-term

Medium-term

Medium-term

Teach the Teacher

Contemporary entrepreneurship education focuses on fostering beneficial attitudes and beliefs, developing cross-functional skills, and preparing people to take responsibility for societal change and sustainability.

The way we effectively help our students to develop such attitudes is constantly changing. Entrepreneurship education, therefore, needs to be continuously revised and updated.

One way of staying up-to-date as an entrepreneurship educator is to participate in “Train the Trainer” programmes that enable entrepreneurship educators to exchange best practices and learn from each other. Having a passionate “champion” figure can motivate and engage others in the entrepreneurial mission.

Similarly, you may seek to form a mentoring relationship with another experienced entrepreneurship educator to gain personal developmental feedback. There are several active entrepreneurship education networks around the world that gladly welcome new members and may guide you in your personal journey as an educator.

Related Cards

Support for Entrepreneurship Initiatives **7**
Educator E-Learning Capabilities **23**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2 Builder, **3** Educator, **4** Internal Performer,
5 Regional Performer, **6** International Performer

Curricular Entrepreneurship Courses

Actions & Formats

Timespan

Incorporate experiential learning projects into your teaching activities.

Short-term

Include mandatory entrepreneurship modules in all degree programmes.

Long-term

Create a double-major or extended curriculum option for students from programmes where they would have restricted or no access to entrepreneurship-related modules.

Long-term

Curricular Entrepreneurship Courses

If you intend to equip your students with an entrepreneurial mindset, related programmes need to be implemented. Applying this to all subject groups and levels ensures that all students have the chance to engage with entrepreneurship as a valuable career path. Moreover, students will value the acquisition of entrepreneurial competences as they develop the entrepreneurial skills and mindsets to help them understand their potential and add value in both an intrapreneurial and entrepreneurial context.

Current best practices in entrepreneurship education generally emphasise experiential learning settings, where students are confronted with challenges that require them to apply theory to real-world scenarios while reflecting on their personal entrepreneurial mindset and related skills. Students learn to identify problems and solutions, bring about the necessary change to implement these solutions, and develop related resilience and leadership skills.

Such courses can be part of an entrepreneurship double-major option or extended curriculum to allow students to both engage with their chosen subject area and acquire entrepreneurial awareness and skills.

Related Cards

Extracurricular Teaching Formats **13**
Experiential Learning Projects **14**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2 Builder, **3** Educator

Extracurricular Teaching Formats

Actions & Formats

Organise entrepreneurship competitions for current students, alumni and external actors.

Run hackathons and start-up weekends with varying themes to attract different audiences.
Recruit entrepreneurship student ambassadors.

Design a public entrepreneurship speaker series.

Set up extracurricular entrepreneurship programmes that are accessible for all students across all disciplines.

Timespan

Short-term

Short-term

Medium-term

Long-term

Extracurricular Teaching Formats

Although entrepreneurship should be embedded in all higher education programmes, it is not always possible to do so.

Therefore, the HEI needs to use innovative ways to promote and ensure a broad level of engagement. Establishing different extracurricular entrepreneurship programmes can be a good way to get started by 'pushing' the entrepreneurial agenda within your HEI. Such programmes usually require fewer resources, are easily approved by the HEI administration, and overall create less initial resistance.

HEI-wide entrepreneurship competitions, subject-related or themed hackathons, and start-up weekends are other options. The HEI could also develop a scheme for recruiting student ambassadors who can act as champions for the entrepreneurial agenda.

Long-term solutions that require more resources include organising stand-alone extracurricular entrepreneurship programmes or establishing an entrepreneur speaker series where entrepreneurs share their stories. This could motivate students and provide a way to engage an internal/external entrepreneurship community that can help with further initiatives.

Related Cards

Teaching Assessments **8**

Curricular Entrepreneurship Courses **12**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

1 Entrepreneurial Aspirant, **2** Builder, **3** Educator

Experiential Learning Projects

Actions & Formats

Include real-world challenges from existing start-ups into your entrepreneurship courses.

Help students frame challenges and learning opportunities around their own start-up ideas.

Introduce entrepreneurial challenges in the classroom provided by companies, public bodies or the HEI itself.

Timespan

Short-term

Short-term

Medium-term

Experiential Learning Projects

Experiential learning is a core element of contemporary best practice in entrepreneurship education. Students learn through guided reflection on their own practice. Based on their previous experiences and external mentorship, they construct new knowledge as well as develop new skills, habits and beliefs by working on real-world problems. This can be enhanced by working in (interdisciplinary) teams that foster mutual debate from various perspectives. Academic or professional mentors continuously provide external stimuli and help students reflect on their experiences.

Experiential learning projects can be created based on various real-world challenges or through collaboration with organisations across various sectors. For example, students could work on a real problem from a start-up at the HEI incubator. Other students may focus on problems related to their own start-ups. Similarly, partnering with established companies may provide other problems for students to work on. Where possible, these challenges may highlight social or societal issues to foster students' appreciation for a more holistic and responsible perspective on entrepreneurship.

Related Cards

Curricular Entrepreneurship Courses **12**
Industry Collaboration **28**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2 Builder, **3** Educator, **4** Internal Performer

Student Clubs or Companies

Actions & Formats

Encourage and support students to start an entrepreneurship club that brings together like-minded students and organises entrepreneurship events.

Facilitate the set up of student companies that provide real-world learning opportunities for students.

Help students join a global student club network and act as one of their faculty advisors.

Timespan

Short-term

Medium-term

Medium-term

Student Clubs or Companies

There are many entrepreneurship learning environments that can be created within a HEI. These environments allow students to experience entrepreneurship first-hand and learn from those experiences through continuous reflection.

For example, entrepreneurship clubs may connect interested students, organise events, invite guest speakers and take part in student competitions. The HEI may also offer a student ambassador programme open to all subject areas to support the coordination of entrepreneurial activities across disciplines. These are effective ways to provide additional learning opportunities.

Students may also decide to become part of an international network such as Enactus, or turn their Student Club into their future job, similar to the students who started the Global Slush Conferences.

Some HEIs have also set-up dedicated student-led companies, where students offer, for example, video creation, copywriting, or other student consulting services to clients under the guidance of academic and industry mentors.

Related Cards

Encourage Entrepreneurship **3**
Experiential Learning Projects **14**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2 Builder, **3** Educator

Entrepreneurship Degree Programmes

Actions & Formats

Establish taught degree programmes for entrepreneurship.

Introduce project-based entrepreneurship degree programmes that include experiential learning.

Timespan

Long-term

Long-term

Entrepreneurship Degree Programmes

Current societal and business challenges are increasingly becoming more complex and ambiguous. Establishing stand-alone entrepreneurship degree programmes allows HEIs to equip their students with the necessary knowledge, skills, and mindset to tackle such challenges as entrepreneurs or corporate innovators.

Entrepreneurship degree programmes can be structured as taught programmes with a more traditional structure, or as fully project-based programmes. In both cases, it is recommended that your learning environment fosters experiential learning through working on current real-world problems. There should be clear collaboration with industry and start-up hubs and innovation centres on campus to enhance this environment.

Establishing such programmes can be challenging. Teaching in such problem-based and cross-functional environments requires a unique teaching approach, and educators need to be trained accordingly. How to deal with the intellectual property created during such programmes can also be challenging. Appropriate legal frameworks should be adopted from the outset to facilitate the spinning out of new start-ups from such programmes.

Related Cards

Curricular Entrepreneurship Courses **12**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

3 Educator, **4** Internal Performer, **5** Regional Performer,
6 International Performer, **7** Guru

Competitions & Awards

Actions & Formats

Host idea competitions, entrepreneurship awards, and prizes for students, alumni, and other target audiences.

Create pitch competitions for more advanced projects and teams.

Introduce themed events that focus on social impact or a current tech trend.

Connect promising entrepreneurs to potential investors through specifically designed events.

Timespan

Short-term

Short-term

Short-term

Medium-term

Competitions & Awards

Hosting and promoting national and international competitions and introducing awards and prizes brings the entrepreneurship community together and generally spurs the development of entrepreneurial HEIs.

These events, awards, and prizes can be framed with different goals in mind. If you are seeking to encourage more of your students to take an entrepreneurial perspective, then awards that recognize outstanding ideas or projects with high social impact are a good way to get started. If your HEI already has an active entrepreneurship ecosystem, you might consider introducing themed or open pitch events. Such formats provide a great platform to spread entrepreneurship within your HEI, involving relevant local stakeholders such as political decision-makers, as well as active investors.

Many HEIs also harness such events as scouting opportunities for their incubation or accelerator programmes. One way of strengthening this connection is by including personalised coaching sessions as prizes for promising ideas, projects and teams.

Related Cards

Extracurricular Teaching Formats **13**

Incubation & Accelerator Programmes **19**

Start-up Funding **20**

Applicable Profiles

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

1 Entrepreneurial Aspirant, **2** Builder, **3** Educator

Entrepreneurship Lab & Incubator Space

Actions & Formats

Provide physical space for start-up teams in your incubation and accelerator programs.

Create a physical entrepreneurship lab that invites continuous experimentation and collaboration between students, educators and start-up teams.

Establish a Makerspace, FabLab or Design Factory within your entrepreneurship lab.

Timespan

Medium-term

Long-term

Long-term

Entrepreneurship Lab & Incubator Space

Having a dedicated physical space for entrepreneurship supports frequent gatherings of the entrepreneurship community connected to your HEI. Such a space can be used to run events and workshops, pitching events, house makerspaces, participate in investment forums, and provide a home on campus. It can also promote chance encounters and collaboration opportunities with other people in the space.

Depending on your local circumstances, such a space might be centrally governed by your HEI or might be a student-led initiative. In both cases, it is important that this space “feels” different to other more traditional classrooms or labs. It needs to invite students and start-up teams to freely explore and prototype continuously, as well as utilise chance encounters and collaboration opportunities with other people in the space.

There are many successful examples of such spaces at HEIs all around the globe. Some have merged into communities of practice and global networks, such as the Design Factory Global Network or the Network of FabLabs. Your HEI should investigate these best practice models and ensure there is a structure in place to facilitate these labs and incubator spaces.

Related Cards

Encourage Entrepreneurship **3**
Incubation & Accelerator Programmes **19**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2 Builder, **3** Educator, **4** Internal Performer

Incubation & Accelerator Programmes

Actions & Formats

Provide individual coaching and mentoring support for nascent start-ups.

Set up cohort-based start-up acceleration programmes for promising start-ups.

Facilitate connections to relevant stakeholders, investors, public funding sources and experienced alumni.

Timespan

Short-term

Medium-term

Medium-term

Incubation & Accelerator Programmes

There are many ways your HEI can help entrepreneurs take their first steps towards proof of concept.

Structured support programmes are one way of providing guidance during the crucial early timeframe of a start-up. Although the distinction between start-up incubation and acceleration may be blurred, there are aspects where both approaches differ. Accelerator programmes may be structured around cohorts of start-up teams who are provided with structured coaching and mentoring for a fixed duration of time – often in exchange for a fixed amount of equity. Incubation programmes are less structured and provide coaching and support more on the individual level. In both cases, one of the best sources of support are fellow entrepreneurs from other projects and start-ups. External coaching should encourage these connections, provide support of their own, and help with engaging other important stakeholders, investors, public funding sources and experienced alumni.

Related Cards

Entrepreneurship Lab & Incubator Space **18**

Start-up Funding **20**

Entrepreneurship Ecosystem **30**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2 Builder, **4** Internal Performer, **7** Guru

Start-up Funding

Actions & Formats

Engage in active matchmaking between start-ups, investors, established companies and experts.

Create specialised matching events.

Act as a trusted partner and advisor for the allocation of public funding for start-ups.

Establish a means of direct start-up investments via your own venture capital (VC) fund or by providing specialised services.

Timespan

Short-term

Medium-term

Medium-term

Long-term

Start-up Funding

Many different funding sources exist for start-ups. Those sources available to founders and their supporters depend on where they are based, their past experience, their supporters amongst other factors. Entrepreneurial HEIs can help start-ups and spin-offs secure necessary funding.

In this regard, a HEI can act as an intermediary and connect start-ups, investors, established companies and subject experts with each other. This matching process can happen through personal introductions, selective pitching events or pen matching summits.

In many countries, various sources of public funding are available to start-ups. HEIs can serve as a specialised match-maker, trusted partner and advisor in the process of connecting start-ups to the various funding programmes.

HEIs may also decide to become investors themselves via their own venture capital funds or providing specialised services in exchange for equity. Regardless of which funding is available, the HEI should always be open to exploring new innovative funding formats.

Related Cards

Entrepreneurship Funding **10**

Competitions & Awards **17**

Entrepreneurship Ecosystem **30**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2 Builder, **4** Internal Performer, **7** Guru

Tech Transfer & Commercialisation

Actions & Formats

Timespan

Offer commercialisation training and workshops to researchers and students to help them experiment with commercialising their research.

Short-term

Create awareness for tech transfer and tech commercialisation throughout your HEI.

Medium-term

Establish a dedicated tech transfer office and tech transfer scouts that provide necessary support.

Medium-term

Tech Transfer & Commercialisation

As places of curiosity, discovery and basic as well as applied research, HEIs are excellent sources of new technologies and applications. Accordingly, HEIs and companies have a vested interest in commercialising intellectual property (IP).

Entrepreneurship provides an effective way by which the commercial potential of new technologies can be discovered and assessed. For example, the creation of spin-off companies can be fostered to develop products and services that utilise new technologies. Similarly, IP can be licensed to established companies and start-ups. However, it is crucial that the underlying technologies and intellectual property are first translated into viable commercial uses.

As part of their entrepreneurship activities, HEIs must provide the necessary internal services relating to commercialisation strategies and related legal implications. They must also create awareness amongst researchers that these paths exist. A dedicated tech transfer office can be employed to for example, provide tech transfer training and assistance, and support protection of IP via patents and copyrights. The HEI should also have a system in place to facilitate commercialisation for student-led projects to ensure it is managed in a way that protects the students.

Related Cards

Entrepreneurship as the Core of HEI Strategy **4**
Establish Entrepreneurial Roles **9**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2 Builder, **4** Internal Performer

General E-Learning Capabilities

Actions & Formats

Provide modern e-learning tools for educators and offer frequent training.

Create the latest e-learning content that is usable across different formats and courses.

Offer parts of your content in the form of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) that are open to a larger audience.

Timespan

Short-term

Medium-term

Medium-term

General E-Learning Capabilities

E-learning is continuing to gain importance across all HEIs, either as supplementary forms of instruction or as stand-alone courses.

Moving to more e-learning based teaching requires you to develop several new capabilities. First, necessary tools and IT infrastructure need to be put in place to enable reliable service and the engagement of teaching environments. Setting up an E-Platform for entrepreneurship educators to share material, show case and make comments is helpful. Second, educators need to adapt their pedagogical approach and experiment with different ways of engaging students. Third, the HEI should provide best practices, guides and templates to improve and refine teaching practices across all programmes and modules. Fourth, resulting implications in relation to adjusting students' workloads and different forms of assessment need to be considered. A measuring tool for effectiveness can be implemented.

In the last few years, it has become quite popular to open up a few select programmes to a wider geographic and demographic audience in the form of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs).

Related Cards

Educator E-Learning Capabilities **23**
IT Infrastructure **25**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

1 Entrepreneurial Aspirant, **2** Builder, **3** Educator

Educator E-Learning Capabilities

Actions & Formats

Timespan

Provide frequent training and support for educators who are new to teaching in virtual environments or who wish to improve their teaching approach.

Medium-term

Connect educators who are teaching in virtual settings and want to exchange insights and best practices, for example via an e-learning forum.

Medium-term

Educator E-Learning Capabilities

Engaging e-learning-based entrepreneurship education requires more than simply providing a few digital teaching tools or a digital platform. Moving to e-learning requires a substantial shift in the general pedagogical approach and specific teaching mechanisms of educators.

HEIs can support their staff during this transition in several ways. For example, best practices, guides and templates can be provided to provide initial reference points when moving your teaching to a digital format. In the long-term, dedicated staff development workshops and events can be introduced to spread gathered learnings throughout the educator community and allow for peer coaching and feedback.

Educators may also draw inspiration from other publicly accessible online entrepreneurship courses, such as the “What, Why & How - Your Road to Entrepreneurship” programme co-funded by the EU Erasmus+ Programme.

Related Cards

General E-Learning Capabilities **22**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

1 Entrepreneurial Aspirant, **2** Builder, **3** Educator

Advanced E-Learning Capabilities

Actions & Formats

Timespan

Cultivate your e-teaching capabilities by establishing a dedicated e-learning centre and support experts.

Long-term

Establish a teaching innovation lab that collects, consolidates and distributes new developments and best practices in education across the HEI.

Long-term

Advanced E-Learning Capabilities

Following the current shift towards more supplementary and stand-alone e-learning programmes and modules, many HEIs have started to consolidate and professionalise their e-learning efforts.

Establishing a teaching innovation lab as a working group or department within your HEI promotes the exploration of new teaching approaches. Such a lab can play a crucial role in collecting and disseminating current best practices in e-learning at your HEI.

Some HEIs have also established a dedicated e-learning centre to highlight the importance of e-learning for their future development and strategy. A dedicated centre may function as a central focal point for e-learning within your HEI and can support educators with professional content creation and the set-up and customisation of learning tools.

Related Cards

General E-Learning Capabilities **22**

Applicable Profiles

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
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3 Educator, **7** Guru

IT Infrastructure

Actions & Formats

Provide a reliable and appropriate student platform that connects students to the relevant services and learning resources.

Offer access to necessary tools and support for digital learning platforms and learning resources.

Timespan

Medium-term

Medium-term

IT Infrastructure

A reliable and working IT infrastructure is the backbone of many HEIs, especially since e-learning, hybrid, and blended learning education is on the rise.

HEIs need to provide the basic hardware and required network capabilities. Then, necessary licenses and teaching tools need to be reviewed and distributed to relevant educators as well as students.

For specific e-learning-heavy environments, students should be able to access programme materials and necessary tools via a user-friendly student platform that, preferably, provides a single sign-on across all connected services. Equally, educators need to be able to quickly and easily design programmes based on templates and best-practices. Such a platform should provide multiple means of communication. Each user should be able to customise their use of the platform by, for example, tailoring communication and notification preferences.

Related Cards

Advanced E-Learning Capabilities **24**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2 Builder, **3** Educator, **4** Internal Performer,
5 Regional Performer, **6** International Performer, **7** Guru

Entrepreneurship Research

Actions & Formats

Establish and incentivise entrepreneurship research activities at your HEI.

Institute an informal entrepreneurship research group that brings together researchers from different departments and fields.

Establish a formal entrepreneurship research group that jointly engages in research and has access to joint funding.

Timespan

Short-term

Short-term

Long-term

Entrepreneurship Research

As an entrepreneurial HEI, you will be engaged in research activity. As an interdisciplinary field of study, entrepreneurship provides a platform for bringing together researchers from various disciplines. Research findings may be disseminated in academic journals, contribute to local and international policy-making, and guide entrepreneurship education best practices.

The general set-up of your entrepreneurship research activities will depend on your institutional structures and budgets. The HEI may first need to put the appropriate research infrastructure in place to support research endeavours. The HEI may decide to establish an informal research group where researchers from different departments meet to exchange relevant findings from their individual fields. This requires a mechanism to identify and support potential research collaborations. You may also decide to formalise such a group by, for example, drafting joint research proposals or raising joint funds. If your HEI has already established a dedicated entrepreneurship centre, related research activities might be centrally coordinated there.

Research can be great for developing industry collaboration and networks.

Related Cards

Networks and Conferences **27**

International Research Partnerships **36**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

4 Internal Performer, **5** Regional Performer,

6 International Performer, **7** Guru

Networks and Conferences

Actions & Formats

Network with start-ups and established businesses to stay up-to-date.

Engage with the public and local community through accessible and open formats.

Join an existing network such as HEInnovate to benefit from collective expertise in the field.

Attend academic and practitioner conferences to form new connections.

Timespan

Short-term

Short-term

Short-term

Medium-term

Networks and Conferences

Networking, public engagement and attending conferences are ways to both disseminate results from one's own research and make beneficial long-term connections.

Networking with start-ups and established businesses is a great way for educators and academics to ensure the relevancy of their teaching and research, and to be up to date with current trending themes and challenges.

Public engagement through open lecture series, workshops, non-academic writing and speaking commitments ensure that your HEI is connected to its local environment and can motivate staff and students to tackle socially relevant issues.

Attending academic and practitioner conferences in one's field allows for lasting connections to be formed and future projects to be set in motion. Attending conferences in other areas also gives the discipline broader exposure.

Your HEI may also join existing professional networks. For entrepreneurial HEIs, the HEInnovate network provides access to a dedicated group of change-makers and experts in the fields of entrepreneurship and innovation.

Related Cards

Entrepreneurship Research **26**

Entrepreneurship Ecosystem **30**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2 Builder, **4** Internal Performer, **5** Regional Performer,

6 International Performer, **7** Guru

Industry Collaboration

Actions & Formats

Use industry collaborations to provide students with relevant current (and future) entrepreneurial opportunities.

Ensure the relevance of ongoing research and open up new research directions by closely collaborating with industry partners.

Extend your collaboration efforts to public stakeholders and local actors within the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Timespan

Medium-term

Medium-term

Medium-term

Industry Collaboration

Maintaining strategic relationships with leading companies – large and small – provides many opportunities and advantages for HEIs.

For students, such relationships may be utilised to provide current real-world experiential learning challenges, interesting class assignments, relevant guest lectures, opportunities for company visits, internships and potentially interesting future job opportunities.

For researchers, collaborating with industry partners ensures the relevancy of their research, opens up new opportunities for new research projects, funding and industry consortium partners for future research proposals.

These efforts should similarly be extended to public stakeholders and actors within your entrepreneurial ecosystem. This allows HEIs to actively shape their own ecosystem and related policies.

To ensure a strong collaboration, a relevant platform and associated structures need to be identified.

Related Cards

Entrepreneurship Funding **10**

Experiential Learning Projects **14**

Applicable Profiles

1 **2** **3** **4** **5** **6** **7**

3 Educator, **4** Internal Performer, **7** Guru

Science Clusters and Parks

Actions & Formats

Become part of an existing science cluster or science park.

Infuse the cluster or science park with entrepreneurial spirit and provide necessary support services.

Establish a science cluster or science park to boost the commercialisation of your research activities and foster a local ecosystem of innovators.

Timespan

Medium-term

Medium-term

Long-term

Science Clusters and Parks

For research-driven HEIs, science clusters or science parks may provide a convenient way of leveraging research findings. By gathering start-ups, SMEs, research departments from established companies, and other collaborating HEIs under one roof, the HEI can create a synergistic ecosystem. Such ecosystems often provide a necessary boost to strengthen and realign regional economies.

Infusing such clusters or science parks with an entrepreneurial spirit can be the catalyst needed to encourage individual residents and stakeholders to envision new products, contemporary service offerings, and novel business models. In such an environment, the actors are generally less constrained by common bureaucracy and stifling organisational frameworks inherent in many HEIs.

There are several networks of such clusters and science parks around the world that provide opportunities to learn from their experiences; these can help you avoid some of the potential pitfalls.

Related Cards

Industry Collaboration **28**

International HEI Partnerships and Networks **31**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 **4** 5 6 7

4 Internal Performer, **7** Guru

Entrepreneurship Ecosystem

Actions & Formats

Act as a trusted market intermediary and engage in matchmaking activities between the different stakeholders within the ecosystem.

Actively build and shape your local entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Timespan

Medium-term

Long-term

Entrepreneurship Ecosystem

HEIs must actively engage in shaping their local entrepreneurship ecosystem. This ecosystem may include nascent and mature start-ups, established companies, public stakeholders, other HEIs, policy advisors and enterprise agencies.

For every striving ecosystem it is important that the participating actors trust each other to share relevant information, talent and resources. HEIs are generally seen as credible entities and may take on the role of a trusted market intermediary within the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Moreover, the HEI must consider cultural aspects as they play a key role in the development of an ecosystem and can help the HEI nurture relevant relationships with key stakeholders.

Striving ecosystems do not always require heavy financial investments and physical structures, such as labs and co-working spaces. What your ecosystem will look like and what its defining features will be, depends on your local circumstances.

Related Cards

Entrepreneurship as the Core of HEI Strategy **4**

Entrepreneurship Lab & Incubator Space **18**

Industry Collaboration **28**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 **4** 5 6 7

4 Internal Performer, **7** Guru

International HEI Partnerships and Networks

Actions & Formats

Timespan

Develop mutual HEI framework agreements with other national and international institutions.

Medium-term

Create a student mobility programme to allow for the flexible and smooth exchange of students between cooperating HEIs.

Medium-term

Establish a staff mobility programme to allow educators and start-up consultants to learn from other HEIs.

Medium-term

International HEI Partnerships and Networks

HEIs currently face a multitude of challenges and need to continuously evolve. Learning from and with other international HEI partners is critical as it encourages the exchange of best practices and strategies and fosters global progress. A mutual partnership agreement between different international HEIs lays the groundwork for close cross-border collaboration.

A student mobility programme allows students to spend time at a partnering HEI and benefit from different educational approaches, inspiring cultural influences and facilitating exposure to other international students.

Similarly, a staff mobility programme allows short- to medium-term exchanges of entrepreneurship staff. For example, such a programme might allow a HEI start-up support consultant to learn from their corresponding colleagues at another institution, or for a researcher to join a research group working in a similar field. For educators, this facilitates personal first-hand exchange of different approaches of entrepreneurship education.

The entrepreneurial agenda of the HEI and its internationalisation strategy should be harmonised.

Related Cards

Joint Start-up Support **34**

Integrated Joint Teaching Activities **35**

International Research Partnerships **36**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 **5** 6 7

5 Regional Performer, **6** International Performer, **7** Guru

Stand-Alone Joint Teaching Activities

Actions & Formats

Timespan

Establish joint teaching activities with other HEIs.

Medium-term

Arrange for mutual guest lectures or coaching sessions between partner HEIs.

Medium-term

Establish international entrepreneurship summer schools or bootcamp initiatives to provide a structured way of welcoming students and educators from partnering institutions.

Medium-term

Stand-Alone Joint Teaching Activities

Establishing joint teaching activities between two or more HEIs allows educators to share different teaching approaches and offers students the opportunity to benefit from learning about entrepreneurship in different cultural settings. Establishing fully integrated joint teaching activities, such as joint degree programmes, is often arduous due to the administrative efforts required. However, your HEI can begin with more simple stand-alone joint teaching activities.

For example, an easier way for entrepreneurship educators from different HEIs to collaborate is to begin with mutual remote or in-person guest lectures. In such cases, parts of the content delivery or student mentoring of an established programme can be led by the teaching partner.

Universities may also decide to run entrepreneurship summer schools or bootcamps that invite students and educators from partnering HEIs to participate and exchange best practices.

Related Cards

Curricular Entrepreneurship Courses **12**

Extracurricular Teaching Formats **13**

Integrated Joint Teaching Activities **35**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 **6** 7

6 International Performer, **7** Guru

Include International Students in Entrepreneurship Education

Actions & Formats

Market your entrepreneurship courses and activities to visiting or permanent international students.

Offer your entrepreneurship courses in English to allow more international students to participate and enrich classroom discussions.

Teach entire entrepreneurship degree programmes in English to attract a more international audience.

Timespan

Short-term

Medium-term

Long-term

Include International Students in Entrepreneurship Education

A more international perspective on entrepreneurship may also be achieved by attracting more visiting or permanent international students.

Many HEIs already have several visiting international students through existing exchange programmes with other institutions. By opening up more entrepreneurship-related courses and teaching these courses in English, local students benefit from an influx of valuable perspectives. In those countries where English is not the first language, some English competency training of local students may be required.

As a HEI, you should also consider whether you could benefit from introducing entire degree programmes geared towards attracting international students by, for example, offering the programme in English, assisting with administrative and visa issues for international students or offering targeted scholarships.

Related Cards

Stand-Alone Joint Teaching Activities **32**

Integrated Joint Teaching Activities **35**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 **3** 4 5 6 7

3 Educator, **5** Regional Performer, **6** International Performer, **7** Guru

Joint Start-up Support

Actions & Formats

Provide opportunities for joint start-up coaching with international HEI partners.

Exchange best practices and provide peer-support in the form of start-up coaching services.

Set up joint virtual incubation or accelerator programmes that do not require physical co-location.

Provide socialisation support and local expertise to start-ups from collaborating HEIs.

Timespan

Short-term

Short-term

Medium-term

Medium-term

Joint Start-up Support

Many HEIs offer various forms of start-up support, such as coaching, funding support, incubator space or accelerator programmes for developing entrepreneurs.

As part of a HEI's internationalisation strategy, some of these activities could be jointly offered with partnering institutions. For example, your start-up coaching capabilities could be made available to entrepreneurs from other HEIs. This allows founding entrepreneurs to benefit from different sets of expertise and perspectives. Such localised support can be especially helpful to founders who are seeking to expand their business to other countries.

Joint coaching programmes allow start-up advisors to exchange best practises and benefit from lessons learned at other HEIs.

Joint virtual acceleration programmes offer structured coaching and support programmes for developing entrepreneurs across entrepreneurial ecosystems.

Related Cards

Incubation & Accelerator Programmes **19**
International HEI Partnerships and Networks **31**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2 Builder, **5** Regional Performer, **6** International Performer,
7 Guru

Integrated Joint Teaching Activities

Actions & Formats

Timespan

Coordinate joint experiential learning projects for students led by industry partners.

Medium-term

Offer joint entrepreneurship degree programmes where each participating HEI is responsible for specific parts of curriculum design and delivery.

Long-term

Integrated Joint Teaching Activities

Establishing fully integrated joint entrepreneurship teaching activities between two or more international HEIs fosters strong long-term ties and partnerships.

Integrating your teaching activities might be achieved by, for example, setting up joint industry-led projects and programmes. This involves students collaborating across different countries and institutions to solve real-life problems for project sponsors from industry. The staff and students work and meet online on a regular basis, and in some cases, might also meet up in person to work together.

HEIs might also decide to strengthen their collaboration by establishing joint entrepreneurship degree programmes where each partnering HEI leads a different part of the programme delivery. During the course of their studies, students spend time at each of the participating institutions – either virtually or on-campus.

Related Cards

International HEI Partnerships and Networks **31**
Stand-Alone Joint Teaching Activities **32**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 **4** 5 6 7

4 Internal Performer, **6** International Performer, **7** Guru

International Research Partnerships

Actions & Formats

Timespan

Develop an international research policy for your HEI that is in-line with your entrepreneurial strategy.

Medium-term

Set up an international office to ease the administrative burden of international research collaborations.

Medium-term

Create international research hubs that allow you to participate in local research clusters in other parts of the world.

Long-term

International Research Partnerships

Contemporary entrepreneurship research relies on international cooperation. HEIs therefore should carefully define their international research policies and strategies. This includes establishing entrepreneurship research teams with members from different nationalities, creating short-term and long-term research exchange opportunities with others, securing funding from international funding schemes, facilitating research partnerships and networks, publishing in international conferences and high impact journals, as well as globally spreading research results across a range of dissemination platforms.

Several research universities have created dedicated entrepreneurship research hubs in other locations to facilitate international research collaborations and strengthen their research profile.

A dedicated international office can help with some of the administrative burdens of inviting international scholars to your HEI or enabling local researchers to spend time at a collaborating institution.

Related Cards

Entrepreneurship Research **26**

International HEI Partnerships and Networks **31**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 **6** 7

6 International Performer, **7** Guru

Student Experience Evaluation

Actions & Formats

Timespan

Design and implement basic programme evaluation systems.

Short-term

Conduct extensive student evaluations via validated frameworks and assessment tools.

Short-term

Evaluate the long-term impact of your education and support programmes via longitudinal studies and feedback from alumni and external stakeholders.

Long-term

Student Experience Evaluation

Most HEIs employ some form of structured evaluation of their programmes and teaching personnel from a student's perspective.

A basic programme evaluation usually takes the form of a digital questionnaire and targets domains such as changes in perceived entrepreneurship knowledge, skills, competencies and attitudes, as well as future entrepreneurial intentions.

There are several validated frameworks that can be used when setting up or improving evaluation processes. Based on the comprehensive EntreComp framework*, a consortium of European HEIs developed the EPIC-tool* to provide fast and actionable feedback for educators as well as an individual evaluation for each student.

A comprehensive evaluation strategy should also measure the long-term impact of educational interventions by, for example, including alumni and external stakeholder feedback.

*EntreComp Framework Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1317&langId=en>

*EPIC tool Link: <https://heinnovate.eu/en/heinnovate-resources>

Related Cards

Internal Evaluation and Indicators **38**

Applicable Profiles

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
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1 Entrepreneurial Aspirant, **2** Builder, **3** Educator

Internal Evaluation and Indicators

Actions & Formats

Evaluate the overall impact of entrepreneurship education at your HEI.

Continuously track entrepreneurial activity indicators and adjust your actions, programmes and strategies accordingly.

Implement and track financial resource indicators and create long-term budget plans.

Timespan

Short-term

Short-term

Short-term

Internal Evaluation and Indicators

Regular internal evaluations of your entrepreneurship activities and entrepreneurial capacity provide indicators that can help you keep track of your progress.

The usefulness of these evaluations depend on the metrics and indicators you define at the outset. For example, common metrics include: the number of start-ups you help create, the number of spin-offs based on research at your HEI, and the amount of funding available for start-up support and entrepreneurship research.

Based on these metrics you can develop more general indicators that help you monitor your development and inform your strategic decisions. For example, general indicators could capture the entrepreneurial activity of your graduates, evaluate the impact of your entrepreneurship education programmes, platform the level of start-up support you provide, and highlight the relevancy and impact of your overall entrepreneurial strategy.

Related Cards

Student Experience Evaluation **37**
Plan and Assess Research Impact **39**
External Evaluation **40**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2 Builder, **3** Educator, **4** Internal Performer,
5 Regional Performer, **6** International Performer, **7** Guru

Plan and Assess Research Impact

Actions & Formats

Create guidelines for how you define research impact and how researchers may improve the impact they are creating.

Continuously measure the impact of your various research activities.

Ensure the relevancy of current and future doctoral researchers by providing appropriate mentoring.

Timespan

Short-term

Medium-term

Long-term

Plan and Assess Research Impact

Research must provide value to the research community, industry stakeholders, policy makers and society at large. This is especially true for entrepreneurship research.

At your HEI, you need to develop an understanding of “what” research impact is, and “how” it can be measured. This includes creating case studies, templates and personal anecdotes from previous research projects and international best-practices on how to translate research findings into tangible value for others.

Your learning from this process should guide the development of your graduate research programmes and provide examples for the necessary “academic rigor” expected of contemporary entrepreneurship research.

Staff training, publicly accessible resources and other outreach activities are needed to continuously raise awareness of the importance of tangible research impact.

Related Cards

Internal Evaluation and Indicators **38**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

3 Educator, **4** Internal Performer, **5** Regional Performer,
6 International Performer, **7** Guru

External Evaluation

Actions & Formats

Incorporate experts or key stakeholders from other HEIs into your evaluation processes as coaches/mentors.

Implement the feedback and recommendations gathered during programme or system accreditation procedures.

Timespan

Short-term

Medium-term

External Evaluation

An external perspective on your HEI's activities can provide benchmarking and new ideas to help you develop your entrepreneurial capabilities.

Such external evaluation might take the form of coaching or mentoring from experienced entrepreneurship educators and administrators from other HEIs. For example, HEInnovate is a joint initiative between several European institutions and can connect you to entrepreneurship experts with a variety of experiences.

External evaluation is often part of different quality assurance processes such as gaining accreditation or national/international funding. During these evaluation and auditing processes, external experts provide an assessment of your HEI's strengths and weaknesses that may help you in further developing your entrepreneurship agenda.

Related Cards

Internal Evaluation and Indicators **38**

Plan and Assess Research Impact **39**

Applicable Profiles

1 2 3 4 5 6 **7**

7 Guru

Towards HEInnovate2.0: From Assessment to Action

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